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FOUNDATIONS FOR THE FUTURE: EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATION AND THE ROLE OF EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

This bibliographical article discusses the importance of early childhood education as a fundamental stage for the integral development of the child, considering cognitive, social, emotional, and cultural aspects. The analysis of scientific literature shows that interactions, play, teacher mediation, and a contextualized curriculum are central elements for promoting meaningful learning. Various authors reinforce that the first years of life represent a decisive phase for the formation of lasting competencies, which requires sensitive, planned pedagogical practices guided by children's rights. The research also reveals the relevance of organized and welcoming school environments, the active participation of families, and respect for diversity. Assessment is treated as a continuous and formative process that should value the individual paths of each child. Furthermore, the influence of technologies and the need for an interdisciplinary approach that breaks with the fragmentation of knowledge are discussed. Finally, it is highlighted that quality in early childhood education depends on the articulation between public policies, teacher training, and an ethical commitment to children's rights. The study reinforces the urgency of an educational practice based on listening, affection, and valuing childhood as a present moment.

Keywords: Childhood. Curriculum. Mediation. Learning.